

ROLE OF COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS IN LIFELONG LEARNING PROCESS

Dr Vidya N Jadhav

Asso. Prof in Education

MVP College of Education Nashik- 2

Abstract :

Communicative means willing and able to talk and show ideas. Lifelong learning is a continuous, self-motivated and voluntary wish to seek additional knowledge. This motivation may be attributed to either personal or professional reasons. Communicative and lifelong learning skills that go beyond specific knowledge or occupational areas. These transferable skills are essential to an individual's intellectual, physical and emotional success regarding of occupational or life role. However communication skills and Lifelong learning skills is about creating and maintaining a positive attitude to learning both for personal and professional development.

Lifelong learning process and communicative skills can enhance our understanding of the world occurred us, provide us with more and improve our quality of life.

Lifelong learning process and communicate skills one of the most effective ways to deal with change in our local communities , governance, associations and organizations. Lifelong learning process and communicative skills develops flexibility in communicating in different ways for example –face to face ,Email, telephone talk ,writing letters ,Reports, Notices, fax messages etc.

Lifelong learning process and development of communicative skills depends on using language that's appropriate to other's in a way that facilitates openness, honesty, and co-operation, providing feedback ,well planned and organization.

Aarhat Publication & Aarhat Journals is licensed Based on a work at <http://www.aarhat.com/eiirj/>

Key words – communicative skills, learning process, transferable skills

Introduction:

Communication is the process of sending & receiving information using a medium that is understand by both the sender & receiver.

- We are constantly communicating with others for different purposes in all spheres of our life at home, school and work and within the community. It is in fact the most important activity for social living.

- Communication thus forms an important and integral part of our lives. In short effective communication will increase productivity of any organization and it is just like the oil that greases the machine.

Definition Of Communication

Communication is who said what to whom what effect –Aristotle

Communication is the sum of all the activities that one person does when he wants to create understanding in the mind of another. It is a bridge of meaning. It involves a systematic process of telling ,listening and understanding -Louis A Allen

Aristotle considered three important components of the communication

1] source 2] Message 3] destination

Lifelong learning is the ‘ongoing, voluntary, and self-motivated ‘ pursuit of knowledge for either personal or professional reasons. Therefore, it not only enhances social inclusion, active citizenship and Personal development, but also self-sustainability, as well as competitiveness and employability.

Importance Of Lifelearning And Communicatve Skills

Communication is a useful tool for information and Lifelong learning process is a self-initiated education that is focused on personal development.

Communication support children’s social and emotional wellbeing and development and Lifelong learning process develop personal development and refer to natural interests, curiosity, and motivations that lead us to learn new things.

Some Hints For Communicative Skills And Lifelong Learning Process

* Self-motivated or self-initiated

Be aware of a person’s facial expressions, tone of voice and body language, to get an idea of how they are feeling

Try to understand the other person’s point of view and don’t jump to conclusion

Self- taught or instruction that is sought

Be flexible in communicating and lifelong learning process in different ways for example –face to face, e-mail, telephone.

Why Lifelong Learning Process And Communicative Skills Are Important

Lifelong learning is important and refers to the voluntary decision to the voluntary decision to enroll in Educational courses or to study a topic on one’s volition. Lifelong learners tend to keep themselves motivated with the desire for more knowledge and self-improvement, or there may be career aspirations in mind.

Communication skills are essential in order to deliver and understand information quickly and accurately. Being able to communicate effectively is perhaps the most important of all life skills.

Developing your communication skills can help all aspects of your life, from your professional life to social gatherings and everything in between.

Role Of Lifelong Learning Skills And Communicative Skills In Learners

- 1] Encourage Learning Ownership. Ultimately we are responsible for our own learning
- 2] Turn Mistakes into Opportunities .The practice of learning from mistakes is one of the best lifelong learning skills anyone can master. The communicative ability of the whale is thought to be highly developed.
- 3] Both creates skills like honesty, trust, love, bonding, creativity, problem solving, logical thinking
- 4] Both skills are important for career development
- 5] Lifelong learners are motivated to learn and develop because they want to;it is deliberate in communicative sills learners are motivated to learn clarity of purpose, clarity of thought, be flexible in communicating in different ways.
- 6] Lifelong Education and communicative skills resulting from integration of formal ,non-formal ,and informal education so as to create ability for continuous development of life which takes place at all times and in all places.
- 7] Communicative and lifelong learning skills that go beyond specific knowledge or occupational areas.

Conclusion :

Lifelong learning process and communicative skills develops flexibility in communicating in different ways. Lifelong learning and communicative skills can enhance our understanding of the world around us, provide us, with more and better opportunities and improve our quality of life.

Reference:

<https://www.valamis.com.hub>.

Dharmendra Mittal, **Communication skill for you**, Arihant Publications Pvt Ltd, Meerut, 2007.

<http://virtualspeech.com>blog>>